

Analysis of the Use of Instagram as a Platform in Learning English Speaking Skill

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Abstract

Technology is integral to schooling in the 4.0 industrial revolution. Technology impacts education, including pupils. Technology affects their sight, hearing, speech, and communication. This research seeks to understand Instagram use in English Bilingual Program. This research uses open interviews so respondents can clearly and thoroughly answer portion-specific questions. Students profit much from learning speaking on Instagram, according to the study. Most said (1) students trust themselves in speaking English, (2) they focus more on perfect grammar while speaking, (3) they can easily fix their friends' posts, and (4) unfavorable comments from friends push them to speak more clearly and fluently.

Keywords: Speaking, Bilingual, Instagram Platform, SMA 1 Pandemawu

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Introduction

Internet access has made it much simpler for people to communicate with one another, conduct research, and obtain information in general, which has facilitated the learning process (Simamora, 2020). If in the past a person needed to physically enter a library in order to seek for information or study materials, all that is required today is access to an internet network in order to obtain any information at any moment it is required. The use of technology is no longer a choice but rather a requirement and a requirement that must be met (Kaplan, 2020).

The growth of social media has been accelerating at a rate that is directly proportional to the rapid growth of technology (Torous et al., 2021). This issue has an effect on the pupils' learning process while they are in class. According to (Babtain, 2021), studying efficiently and utilizing the appropriate kind of technology is one of the most effective strategies to increase the likelihood that students will achieve success in their academic pursuits. In addition, maintaining a positive mindset and keeping the participant's education as the primary emphasis is also essential (Zulfikar et al., 2019).

It is becoming more accepted that students' use of social media can greatly influence

their academic performance (Cheng et al., 2020). A social networking platform with all of its flaws as an alternative learning medium (Zhao & Zhou, 2020). Due to the fact that they are designed to foster supportive communities, disseminate native languages, and stimulate interactions outside of class, social networking sites (SNS) are held in high regard within the academic community as being extremely helpful in the process of language acquisition (Reinhardt, 2019).

The prevalence of social media has a significant effect on students (Sobaih et al., 2020). A growing number of students are utilizing their laptops or mobile devices to access social networking sites and spend their time there. Learners even have accounts that they administer on their own so that they can communicate socially with their friends and even new people all around the world (Hammer et al., 2021). Therefore, this is something that can be modified by the educator or teacher in order to construct specialized activities that make use of social media in the process of learning the language. Instagram is a useful tool for instructors to employ in order to maintain communication with the participants in their classes (Carpenter et al., 2020).

The fact that students are already familiar with the platform is the primary argument in favor of using Instagram as a type of instructional media. This argument is supported by the fact that students currently use Instagram (Pujiati et al., 2019), even further. Because almost all students already have a laptop and other electronic device, educators don't need to spend a lot of money to implement it. In addition to that, using Instagram doesn't require any special training, so it can be easily implemented at any educational level.

Instagram gives students the authority to create digital content themselves and publish it online, in addition to the fact that it can stimulate activity students and educators in teaching; (1) support teaching for learning throughout life; Instagram can be used by every level of education; (2) Instagram can stimulate activity students and educators in teaching; and (3) Instagram allows for collaboration between students and educators on a specific project or assignment. In addition to that, there are several other reasons that can be used as material consideration to make Instagram a media learning platform (Erarslan, 2019).

Students are ready to technological changes in learning (Oke & Fernandes, 2020). At the moment Facebook, Twitter and Instagram is the most popular SNS platform popular (Laor, 2022). As a consequence of this, the system can be utilized as a tool for learning, which results in an effect that is beneficial to the process of acquiring language abilities. Instagram was launched on October 2010 and its development very fast (Leaver et al., 2020). Instagram got one million users with only one month after officially launched in April 2015, the number

of users has reached 300 million active users, this growth is faster than other popular social media such as Facebook, twitter, blog and My Space (Mou, 2020).

Indonesia is ranked 4th country with Most active Instagram users in 2019 (Indonesian Digital Reports, 2019). Here are the countries who ranked in the top 4 with the number of Instagram users most in the world which if sorted are: (1) United States total users 110 million or 33.44 percent of the total population; (2) Brazil total users 66 million or 31.38 percent of the total population; (3) India total users 64 million or 4.68 percent of the total population; (4) Indonesia has a total of 56 million users or 20.97 percent of the total population (Arman & Sidik, 2019). In Indonesia, Instagram user most are from the age range of 18 years to 24 years for men and woman.

Instagram delivers amazing opportunity to Language learning for teachers and student. (Teng et al., 2022). Instagram provides a way new for students to learn language and culture critically, apart from that, it also helps participants educate to reflect on the process meaningful learning (Sakr, 2020). Via Instagram, students can practice 4 skills in English at the same time.

There some relevance studies that related to this research in the previous. The first research entitled, "The Use of Instagram as a Mobile-Assisted Language Learning Tool" was compiled by (Gonulal, 2019). The present study sought to explore how English language learners (ELLs) used Instagram, a popular social networking site, for language learning purposes and to reveal their attitudes towards and experiences in using it as a mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) tool. Special interest was also placed on whether there were any distinct ELL profiles in using Instagram for independent and informal language learning. In this mixed-methods study, both quantitative and qualitative data were concurrently collected through an online comprehensive survey consisting of three sections. Ninety-seven Instagram using ELLs took part in this study. Basic descriptive statistics and a cluster analysis were conducted on the quantitative data, and a thematic analysis on the qualitative data. The results showed that Instagram has the potential to help ELLs to improve overall language skills in general, and vocabulary and communication skills in particular. Further, ELLs' experiences in using Instagram as a MALL tool for informal language learning were largely positive. Additionally, two different language learner profiles (i.e., novice and experienced) emerged based on Instagram use habits and orientations. Overall, this study indicated that social networking platforms and MALL applications can be used as an effective mobile language learning tool.

Second, the research entitled, "Instagram: How Do Students View on it in Speaking

Classroom” was arranged by (Devi, et al, 2021). The emergence of the 4.0 era requires the world of education to adapt to technology. Practicing and learning English can take the advantage of the sophisticated technology, especially applications that can be downloaded from students' smart phone. Students acknowledge that English learning done in the classroom is easy for them to forget because it is rarely used in everyday life. Practices done in the classroom do not have enough time for all students to speak English, and students are less motivation to speak English outside the classroom. Integrating Instagram into the process of teaching English speaking is believed could motivate students to speak and increase their speaking ability. Various features on Instagram can help students in doing assignments. Tasks may be packaged attractively within the variety of videos based on a certain theme and uploaded to Instagram. This study aimed to determine students' perceptions related to the use of social media Instagram in learning English speaking. This descriptive study used forty-four students Communication Science in academic year 2019/2020 who took Bahasa Inggris Keahlian. To determine students' perceptions, researchers used questionnaire adopted from Dornyei, 2011. The results of the study showed a positive or good response on students' perceptions towards the use of Instagram in learning English Speaking. Furthermore, Instagram can be used as another medium in teaching speaking. This is strengthened by the increase in self-confidence, learning motivation, and student interest in speaking in English.

Third, the research entitled, “Determining How Social Media Affects Learning English: An Investigation of Mobile Applications Instagram and Snap Chat in TESOL Classroom” was conducted by (Fadda & Hind, 2020). The purpose of this research paper was to explore the effects of social media in learning English speaking and reading skills. Although social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Snapchat, are mostly used socially and for marketing, they also have a significant impact on learning English. In determining how social media affects learning English, this paper will be focusing on mobile Apps; Snapchat and Instagram. The paper investigates how user attitude, experience, and perception influence the use of Instagram and Snapchat in learning the English language in a classroom. The research was done on different databases, including Academic Search Complete, Education Source, ERIC, Library, Information Science, and Technology Abstracts, and Professional Development Collection. Research shows that learners with social media accounts are less enthusiastic about learning English, even if it means recreational reading. This differs from the learners without user accounts whose attitude of learning English speaking skills is positive. This research paper concludes that, in comparison to Snapchat, Instagram is a more effective social

media platform for engaging and learning of the English language. This contributes to a greater understanding of the English language and its culture while providing more practical knowledge and promoting interactions. However, more research is needed to determine the impact of Snapchat on learning English speaking skills.

Fourth, the research entitled, “Social Networking and Language Learning: Use of Instagram (IG) for Evaluating Oral Communication Skill” was drafted by (Çakmak, 2020). This chapter gives a brief overview on the use of social network sites (SNSs) for language learning and presents an empirical study of the use of Instagram (IG), one of the most popular SNSs, to assess learners' oral communication skills in the foreign language classroom. Several studies have mainly revealed the perceptions and preferences of learners in regards to using SNSs for learning grammar, vocabulary, L2 writing, reading, and speaking. In the current study, the performance scores of participants on an oral communication speaking task delivered both on IG and in class, as well as their scores on the Big Five personality traits as measured by the Quick Big Five Personality Test (QBFPT), were examined statistically. The results demonstrate IG facilitated students' performance in oral communication skill significantly and that personality traits do not predict the performance on IG, but the extroverted and conscientious are highly likely to achieve high scores in classroom.

Lastly, the research entitled, “Integrative Task-Based Learning: Developing Speaking Skill and Increase Motivation via Instagram” was compiled by (Binti Azlan et al., 2019). The ability to communicate fluently and accurately is becoming one of the most important components of language elements in Malaysia. Some of the factors that cause to the inability to speak eloquently are low self-confidence, inadequate practices and less exposure to the language. Henceforth, this action research aimed to discover the potential use of integrating Instagram features and task-based learning activities to develop speaking skills and identify the level of pupils' motivation. In this study, an observation and semi structured oral interview were conducted as methods for data collection. Hence, eight pupils from an urban pre-school in Selangor and low level of English proficiency in a rural primary school in Negeri Sembilan, Malaysia were selected. The findings from the action research indicated that a majority of the pupils acknowledged that Instagram motivates and boosts their interest to practice English speaking and at the same time improve their speaking skills. It is concluded that incorporating of Instagram and task-based learning activities are aligned with the needs of 21st Century learning and teaching strategies together with the potential to engage and motivate pupils in developing their speaking skills.

A few researchers focused on how Instagram is used as a media to enhance student's

speaking skill through Bilingual Program at the SMA 1 Pandemawu. In the end, it will be important to determine what good influence was acquired by pupils in order to develop their ability in English's four competencies.

Research Method

The descriptive qualitative method is being used for this investigation. The responders that were chosen are students in their first semester at the SMA 1 Pandemawu, where they are currently enrolled in English classes. The total number of respondents was 19, all of them belonged to the same class. All of the respondents were given questions in an open interview to determine whether or not knowing how to use Instagram may increase their performance in the four English abilities.

Following the completion of the interview, the researchers engaged in conversation with focus groups in order to get further information regarding the utilization of Instagram as a medium for English language learning courses. The interview instrument consists of twenty questions that are sent anonymously to all respondents. After the interview is over, the results are typed up, and then the process is repeated with the stages that follow: (1) interview results are transcribed into field notes (field notes), and the researchers remark on and evaluate each discovery. (2) The reduction of data, which involves processes such as analyzing, selecting, concentrating, and discarding information that is extraneous to the topic of research that has finally been assigned a code (coding), (3) presenting data and assembling information that is descriptively or narratively relevant to the issue formulation of this research, which is specifically to find out how to use Instagram in language classes taught in English, (4) Come to your own conclusions and check them.

Before we got started with the interview, we gave each student a separate assignment to make a long video out of a short one, which they then published to their own personal Instagram account. The information that is produced needs to use English that is grammatically correct, as well as proper pronunciation, spelling, and word choice. This is the reason why information needs to be posted to your personal account so that students can be conscious when they are making blunders or mistakes when speaking English. Once the content has been published to the student's personal account, they will be requested to tag the post this to three of his friends and lecturers who offer English Courses. Following this, lecturers and friends who have previously marked the post will remark on it using English.

Result and Discussion

The researchers wanted to know the findings gained from the students, therefore they collected data to find out how well the students could speak English from the English Department of the SMA 1 Pandemawu in speaking English, and they did this by observing and interviewing students. In addition, researchers carried out study by examining the actions of students as well as the instruction given during the course of a bilingual program's teaching and learning process. During the process of learning, the researchers discovered that some students were less proficient in speaking English, and that there were also a number of students who were able to increase their ability to speak English as a result of participating in the bilingual program. They are not aware of the significance of adhering to the program in order to make their English sound more natural while they are speaking the language. On the other hand, the researchers also pay attention to what the students are doing when they are not in class. The researchers have not noticed any changes in the ways in which students communicate, and they report that pupils still only sometimes use English inside or outside of the classroom. Because of this finding, it is possible to draw the conclusion that the student knowledge of improving English-speaking abilities through bilingual programs at SMA 1 Pandemawu is still relatively low, and that only a small number of students have been successful in increasing their English talk speaking through the program.

On the other hand, the researchers also monitored the activities of the students when they were not in class. The researchers have not noticed any changes in the ways in which students communicate, and they report that pupils still only sometimes use English inside or outside of the classroom. Because of this finding, it is possible to draw the conclusion that student awareness at SMA 1 Pandemawu regarding enhancing English speaking abilities through bilingual programs is still limited, and that only a small number of students can successfully enhance their English-speaking skills as a result of participating in the program.

The researchers sought to provide the correct research results in the correct and statistical error in detecting when the research was made by the students after performing a statistically interview before moving any further into the talks that are associated with the results of the research. This was done before further stepping into the discussions associated with the results of the research. The type of research that is mentioned in this term focuses on the comprehension and ability of students to improve their language skills by speaking English through the usage of bilingual programs. Additionally, several questions referring to sentences that match the meticulous to see understanding and student's capacity in increasing their language skills in speaking English through the bilingual program are given to participants.

Students at the SMA 1 Pandemawu will be able to participate in a bilingual program on the campus, which will help them improve their command of the English language. A bilingual program is one that teaches students how to learn and train themselves to speak English, as well as how to develop their ability to speak English. This type of program is called a "bilingual program." However, only some of the students in this bilingual program are effective in improving their English speaking abilities. The program is only successful for some of the students.

Following the collection of data through observations, the researchers engage in interviews that are semi-structured. The interviews with the participants were conducted during this term by the researchers. In addition, students are given monologue questions to answer about the degree to which they find it easy or difficult to fulfill the requirements of the bilingual program.

The researchers concluded, on the basis of the interview, that the majority of students had low frequency experiences in following the bilingual program while they practiced speaking, and just a few of them had average frequency experiences. In addition, it appears that pupils that participate in the program fare worse when it comes to speaking. It is also possible to describe it as their speaking abilities while they are participating in the bilingual program. Because of this poor aptitude, they are also unequal when speaking in English.

How to design a bilingual program with the goal of enhancing one's linguistic capabilities in accordance with the knowledge and skills gained through participation in a bilingual program. Because in this Bilingual program we have taught how to speak English easily and effectively, it is a Bilingual program in SMA 1 Pandemawu that has its own system and program that makes us better understand and faster responding to what the tutor told by themselves. The program itself is very good and effective programs that can keep us who follow this program more reliable talking to foreign discussions. According to the student at the SMA 1 Pandemawu who participated in the bilingual program and was able to significantly increase their capacity to communicate in English as a result of their participation in the program.

The bilingual program makes it difficult to improve one's ability to speak English. This is one of the reasons why, in addition to the fact that I do not like it and the materials presented do not contain a clear explanation or description of anything else, the bilingual program is also too affected by the fact that it is too close in proximity to other courses, which makes it difficult for me to concentrate and therefore makes me lazy. There are certain breaks that do a response to the hourly billing, but there are also many people who disagree with this because we impact the less concentrate in following the activity obtained, which is not science but

tiresome and fair. A student at the SMA 1 Pandemawu stated that it is difficult for him to develop his English abilities by participation in bilingual programs.

Because students from the SMA 1 Pandemawu believe that it is both easy and challenging to enhance one's linguistic abilities by participating in a bilingual program, it is possible for us to determine the factors that lead to students finding it challenging to participate in such a course. The findings of this study lend credence to the assertion that English-speaking students at SMA 1 Pandemawu make errors in the language, particularly when they communicate in English. This can be seen from the findings that were made in a way that indicates that their knowledge, understanding, and capacity to communicate is still less even if there were just a few achievements. This study discovered that the majority of relevant errors were brought about by a lack of student engagement in bilingual programs.

As a result, it is essential for the English language programs at the SMA 1 Pandemawu to provide students with classes that include more content about communicating effectively in English by everyday conversations. In addition, English language instruction in mediums other than bilingual programs needs to be made available to students at the university and at agencies affiliated with the university.

Conclusion

At the SMA 1 Pandemawu, learning English is required of all students as one of the general education requirements. It's a Pandemawu district. This class is for a total of 2 credits and has a combined total of 14 in-person and online sessions for instruction. The goal of an English course is to teach pupils general English, and the course will cover all four of the following English skills: (1) reading, (2) speaking, (3) listening, and (4) writing.

Students at the SMA 1 Pandemawu who are enrolled in first-semester English classes are taught how to use Instagram as part of their media literacy curriculum. researchers attempted to apply their findings to many aspects of public speaking. Every single student has different assignments, one of which is to film a video in the English language in which they play themselves, which is then submitted to your account on their personal Instagram. At this point, the researcher has not placed any restrictions on the kind of content that can be uploaded.

Based on the findings of interviews and discussions held with focus groups, the researchers came to the following conclusions: (1) Students have a high level of self-assurance when it comes to using English in conversation; (2) more students Pay attention to the correct usage of grammar when speaking, (3) students find it simpler to remedy speech faults made

by his friends, and (4) the negative remarks that his buddy gave motivated students to speak in a way that was more clear and fluid.

References

- Arman, A. A., & Sidik, A. P. (2019). Measurement of Engagement Rate in Instagram (Case Study: Instagram Indonesian Government Ministry and Institutions). 2019 International Conference on ICT for Smart Society (ICISS), 7, 1–6.
- Babtain, A. (2021). The Effect of McGraw-Hill Education Connect on Students' Academic Performance. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 16(3), 86–113.
- Binti Azlan, N. A., Zakaria, S., & Yunus, M. (2019). Integrative Task-Based Learning: Developing Speaking Skill and Increase Motivation via Instagram. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v9-il/5463>
- Çakmak, F. (2020). Social Networking and Language Learning: Use of Instagram (IG) for Evaluating Oral Communication Skill. In *Recent Tools for Computer- and Mobile-Assisted Foreign Language Learning* (pp. 110–131). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-1097-1.ch005>
- Carpenter, J. P., Morrison, S. A., Craft, M., & Lee, M. (2020). How and why are educators using Instagram? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 96, 103149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103149>
- Cheng, W. W. H., Lam, E. T. H., & Chiu, D. K. W. (2020). Social media as a platform in academic library marketing: A comparative study. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 46(5), 102188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2020.102188>
- Devi, et al. (2021). How do Students View on it in Speaking Classroom | JURNAL BASIS. (2021). <https://ejournal.upbatam.ac.id/index.php/basis/article/view/2435>
- Erarslan, A. (2019). Instagram as an Education Platform for EFL Learners. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology - TOJET*, 18(3), 54–69.
- Fadda, A. A., & Hind. (2020). Determining How Social Media Affects Learning English: An Investigation of Mobile Applications Instagram and Snap Chat in TESOL Classroom (SSRN Scholarly Paper 3581296). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3581296>
- Gonulal, T. (2019). The Use of Instagram as a Mobile-Assisted Language Learning Tool. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 10(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cet.590108>
- Hammer, M., Scheiter, K., & Stürmer, K. (2021). New technology, new role of parents: How parents' beliefs and behavior affect students' digital media self-efficacy. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 116, 106642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2020.106642>
- Kaplan, B. (2020). Revisiting Health Information Technology Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues and Evaluation: Telehealth/Telemedicine and Covid-19. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 143, 104239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2020.104239>
- Laor, T. (2022). My social network: Group differences in frequency of use, active use, and interactive use on Facebook, Instagram and Twitter. *Technology in Society*, 68, 101922.
- Leaver, T., Highfield, T., & Abidin, C. (2020). Instagram: Visual social media cultures. John Wiley & Sons.
- Mou, J. B. (2020). Study on social media marketing campaign strategy—TikTok and Instagram [Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology]. <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/127010>
- Oke, A., & Fernandes, F. A. P. (2020). Innovations in Teaching and Learning: Exploring the Perceptions of the Education Sector on the 4th Industrial Revolution (4IR). *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(2), 31. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc6020031>
- Pujiati, H., Zahra, & Tamela, E. (2019). The Use of Instagram to Increase Students' Motivation and Students' Competence in Learning English. 651–656. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icesshum-19.2019.103>
- Reinhardt, J. (2019). Social media in second and foreign language teaching and learning: Blogs, wikis, and social networking. *Language Teaching*, 52(1), 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444818000356>
- Sakr, M. (2020). 'It just opened my eyes a bit more': Student engagement with Instagram to develop understanding of complex concepts. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 25(7), 858–871. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562517.2019.1613356>
- Simamora, R. M. (2020). The Challenges of Online Learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Essay Analysis of Performing Arts Education Students. *Studies in Learning and Teaching*, 1(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.46627/silet.vli2.38>
- Sobaih, A. E. E., Hasanein, A. M., & Abu Elnasr, A. E. (2020). Responses to COVID-19 in Higher Education: Social Media Usage for Sustaining Formal Academic Communication in Developing Countries. *Sustainability*, 12(16), Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12166520>
- Teng, C., Heydarnejad, T., Hasan, Md. K., Omar, A., & Sarabani, L. (2022). Mobile assisted language learning in learning English through social networking tools: An account of Instagram feed-based tasks on learning

- grammar and attitude among English as a foreign language learner. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1012004>
- Torous, J., Bucci, S., Bell, I. H., Kessing, L. V., Faurholt-Jepsen, M., Whelan, P., Carvalho, A. F., Keshavan, M., Linardon, J., & Firth, J. (2021). The growing field of digital psychiatry: Current evidence and the future of apps, social media, chatbots, and virtual reality. *World Psychiatry*, 20(3), 318–335. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20883>
- Zhao, N., & Zhou, G. (2020). Social Media Use and Mental Health during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Moderator Role of Disaster Stressor and Mediator Role of Negative Affect. *Applied Psychology: Health and Well-Being*, 12(4), 1019–1038. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aphw.12226>
- Zulfikar, T., Dahliana, S., & Sari, R. A. (2019). An Exploration of English Students' Attitude towards English Learning. *English Language Teaching Educational Journal*, 2(1), 1–12.